

Effect of Phototherapy on Serum Calcium Level in Neonatal Jaundice**K. Krishnaprabha¹, R. Menaha², S. Aruna³, S. Dhanapriya⁴, K. Suganya⁵**^{1,2,3}Department of Biochemistry, Government Medical College, Karur, Tamil Nadu, India⁴Department of Biochemistry, Government Medical College, Kallakurichi, Tamil Nadu, India⁵Department of Physiology, Sri Ramachandra Medical College & Research Institute, Porur, Chennai, Tamilnadu, India

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Corresponding Author: Dr. S.Dhanapriya

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Background:** Neonatal jaundice observed during first week of life is mainly attributed to the physiological immaturity of the liver to handle the increased bilirubin production. Though phototherapy is an effective treatment for neonatal jaundice, its potential effect on serum calcium levels should be monitored.**Aim:** To study the effect of phototherapy on serum calcium level in term neonates with unconjugated hyperbilirubinemia.**Methodology:** Total Serum Bilirubin and Serum Calcium (Total) was measured before and 48 hours after phototherapy.**Conclusion:** Decrease in serum calcium levels occurs in neonates exposed to phototherapy. Hence serial monitoring of serum Calcium should be done as a routine investigation along with serum bilirubin level in neonates receiving phototherapy.**Keywords:** Neonatal jaundice, Bilirubin, Calcium, Phototherapy.

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Introduction

Neonatal jaundice is a yellowish discoloration of skin, sclera and mucous membrane due to high bilirubin levels. It is observed during first week of life in approximately 60 % of term and 80 % of preterm neonates [1]. Neonatal jaundice is mainly attributed to the physiological immaturity of the liver to handle the increased bilirubin production. It can be physiological or pathological. In most of the cases, it is benign and no intervention is required [2]. Approximately 5-10% of them have clinically significant jaundice that requires intervention depending on various factors like age of the child, serum bilirubin level and the underlying cause [3]. The treatment modalities include frequent feeding, phototherapy and exchange transfusion [4]. If untreated, it leads to severe unconjugated hyperbilirubinemia which is potentially neurotoxic.

Phototherapy changes the structure of bilirubin and thus increases its excretion: currently the standard treatment for neonatal jaundice. It is the routine method for management of hyperbilirubinemia. It causes photo oxidation of bilirubin into water soluble, less lipophilic, colourless form of bilirubin which is readily excreted in bile, faeces and urine. It alleviates the need for exchange transfusion [6]. Though it is a non-invasive technique, It can produce various side effects such as skin rashes,

temperature instability, feeding intolerance, loose stools, dehydration, retinal damage, redistribution of blood flow, hypocalcemia, bronze baby syndrome, and genotoxicity [5].

Calcium is an important element in the body and phototherapy can lead to the decrease of serum calcium levels. On the other hand, decrease in calcium can cause certain complications such as apnea, muscular tick convulsion, and decrease in absorption of vitamin D, which causes a decrease in the absorption of calcium [6].

Therefore, any changes in the blood level cause irreparable effects, and might also influence the absorption of other elements. Research has shown that phototherapy can cause a significant decline in serum calcium levels in newborns with jaundice [7]. The exact mechanism of how phototherapy affects serum calcium levels is not fully understood, but it's thought to be related to the suppression of melatonin secretion, which in turn affects cortisol levels and bone calcium uptake [8]. Though phototherapy is an effective treatment for neonatal jaundice, healthcare providers should be aware of its potential effect on serum calcium levels and monitor newborns accordingly.

Aim & Objective: To study the effect of phototherapy on serum calcium level in term neonates with unconjugated hyperbilirubinemia. 50 term neonates of either gender with unconjugated hyperbilirubinemia, planned for phototherapy were considered for the study. Serum bilirubin and calcium levels were measured before and 48 hours after phototherapy.

This cross-sectional study was conducted at Thanjavur Medical College, Thanjavur during the period of October 2018 – November 2018. Total Serum Bilirubin & Serum Calcium (Total) were measured before and 48 hours after phototherapy.

Methodology:

Total Serum Bilirubin was measured by Diazo method & Serum Calcium (Total) was measured by Arsenazo III method before and 48 hours after phototherapy [6]. During phototherapy babies were monitored for symptoms of hypocalcemia and if present, they were managed as per standard regimen.

Inclusion Criteria: Neonates who were stable and having unconjugated hyperbilirubinemia requiring phototherapy as per AAP guidelines 2011 and NICE guidelines 2016 and neonates who require phototherapy for more than 48 hours were included for the study.

Exclusion Criteria: Icteric neonates who had exchange transfusion, patients suffering from birth asphyxia, congenital malformation, sepsis, hypothyroidism, infant of diabetic mother, infant of mothers who were on anti-convulsants, ABO/Rh incompatibility, serum calcium level less than 8 mg/dl before phototherapy, neonates who required phototherapy for less than 48 hours were excluded from the study.

Statistical analysis: Data were analyzed using Microsoft Excel 2013. Mean and Standard Deviation were calculated. Student's t test was used to compare mean values between two groups. For all statistical evaluations, a two-tailed probability of value <0.05 was considered significant.

Results:

Table 1: Serum total bilirubin and calcium levels before & after phototherapy

S. No.	Parameters	Before Phototherapy (Mean ±SD)	After Phototherapy (Mean ±SD)	p value
1	Serum Total Bilirubin (mg/dl)	14.82 ± 1.6	10.75 ± 1.4	<0.001 significant
2	Serum Calcium (mg/dl)	8.97 ± 0.45	7.65 ± 0.51	0.002 significant

Figure 1: Serum total bilirubin levels before & after phototherapy

Figure 2: Serum calcium levels before & after phototherapy

Figure 3: Distribution of serum calcium levels before & after phototherapy

Figure 4: Frequency distribution of calcium levels after phototherapy

After 48 hours of phototherapy, there was a significant decrease (p value 0.002) in serum calcium levels in 33 neonates (66%). 2 neonates (4%) were clinically symptomatic and managed as per the regime.

Discussion

Phototherapy is the mainstay of treating hyperbilirubinemia in neonates where insoluble bilirubin (unconjugated) is converted into soluble isomers that can be excreted in urine and faeces [8]. Bilirubin absorbs light maximally in the blue range (460-490 nm). CFL / LED phototherapy is most commonly used with four blue and two white (for examination purpose) lights but this combination can be replaced with 6 blue lights in order to increase the irradiance output.

Ionized calcium is needed for many biochemical processes including blood coagulation, neuromuscular excitability, cell membrane integrity, function and cellular enzymatic and secretory activity. Hypocalcaemia increases cellular permeability to sodium ions and increased cell membrane excitability. The symptoms when present may be of neuromuscular irritability, myoclonic jerks, jitteriness, laryngospasm, exaggerated startle, seizures and abnormalities of cardiac function & ECG [9].

Srinivasa et al., suggested that hypocalcemia was caused due to a reduction in parathormone secretion in jaundiced neonates who were treated with phototherapy [10]. Eghbalian F & Monsef A stated that higher level of urinary calcium excretion was proposed to be the cause of hypocalcemia in phototherapy treated jaundiced neonates [11]. Rashi et al., observed that 75% of term & 90% of preterm developed hypocalcaemia after phototherapy [12]. Shrivastva et al, in 2015 also observed hypocalcemia effect of phototherapy in 30.0% of term neonates [13]. Our result clearly correlates with the previous studies done by Rosario et al., where 7.5% neonates developed hypocalcemia after receiving phototherapy [14]. A study published 2015 found that the serum calcium level in newborns decreased significantly after phototherapy, from 9.15 ± 0.81 mg/dL to 8.82 ± 0.93 mg/dL [15]. Another study found that 12.5% of newborns developed hypocalcemia (serum calcium < 8 mg/dL) after phototherapy [16]. In our study, hypocalcemia was observed in 66% of neonates after phototherapy. These observations conclude that a decrease in serum calcium levels occurs in neonates exposed to phototherapy. Hence serial monitoring of serum Calcium should be done as a routine investigation along with serum bilirubin level in neonates receiving phototherapy.

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